

Re-claiming one's "culture": how middle-class capital and participation in higher education can promote the assertion of ethnic identities.

Abstract

This paper explores the narratives of British-born young women of Bangladeshi heritage to examine the influence of social class and university participation on ethnic identification. As UK-born young people of minority ethnic origins access higher education in growing numbers, questions about their socio-cultural incorporation are increasingly salient. This article draws on interviews with 21 female undergraduates of Bangladeshi background. It investigates their understandings and constructions of their ethnic identities and underlying processes related to class location and trajectory. This is conceptualised following Bourdieu as an amalgam of economic, cultural and social capital. Findings highlight: how middle-class capital can be drawn on in the construction of a "positive" ethnic identity; how intersecting ethnicised and classed hierarchies of value can hamper the development of a positive conception of one's ethnicity and lead to "self-distancing"; and how participation in higher education can favour the re-evaluation and "re-claiming" of ethnic identities by promoting exposure to new and valued interpretive repertoires of what it means to be Bangladeshi. They reveal the fluid, relational character of the meanings and value attached to ethnic categories by young people of minority ethnic background, and the significance of economic, social and cultural capital in informing these meanings.

Keywords

Ethnic identification, class, social mobility, education, Bourdieu

Introduction

This paper examines how middle-class status and participation in higher education (HE) contribute to inform the ethnic identification of British-born young women of Bangladeshi origins. Consequently, it sheds light on the influence of socio-economic position and trajectory on processes of ethnic identity construction among young people of minority ethnic background. With the UK minority ethnic population in continuous growth, from 13% to 20% of residents between 2001 and 2011 (Jivraj 2012), questions around the socio-cultural incorporation of immigrants and their descendants have assumed increasing salience. Studies in social psychology indicate that "ethnic private regard", i.e. holding a positive conception of one's ethnicity, importantly contributes to individuals' well-being (Phinney 1990; Yip 2016). Yet, these studies also point to the "identity threat" deriving for those of minority ethnic origins from such an identity being attributed lesser value in mainstream social and institutional settings such as schools and work-places. In the UK as elsewhere in Europe, public and policy discourses have substantially shifted since the turn of the century from the promotion of "multiculturalism" to a preoccupation with "community cohesion" and a "shared British identity", especially in the aftermath of the 2001 northern towns riots and 2005 London bombings (Cantle 2001; Kundnani 2002). These discourses are often underpinned by essentialist notions of minority and majority ethnic identities as homogeneous, fixed and mutually exclusive (Rodriguez-Garcia 2010). Strong identification with one's ethnic group on the part of young people of minority ethnic origins tends therefore to be seen as problematic, as it is assumed to signal an inability or unwillingness to integrate.

Within this context, evidence of upward social mobility among the younger generations and increasing class differentiation within minority ethnic groups (Platt 2005; CoDE 2014) call for the investigation of identification patterns and trends among middle-class and upwardly mobile individuals. Women of Bangladeshi heritage in particular, and more generally of South Asian Muslim origins, have long been the object of concerns over a lack of “integration”, with their low rates of education and labour market participation being often attributed to the constraining influence of patriarchal norms imposed by their “culture” (Ahmad 2007; Ahmed and Dale 2008). Despite most of them coming from low socio - economic backgrounds, the numbers of those attending university has however grown considerably over the last two decades (Lymperopoulou and Parameshwaran 2015; Bagguley and Hussain 2016). It thus remains to be seen how increasing participation in HE and upward social mobility contribute to inform these women’s sense of belonging to a commonly stigmatised ethnic group and the meanings they attach to this ethnic identity category.

This article aims to further the understanding of these dynamics by providing an in-depth analysis of narratives of (de -)attachment and (non -)belonging to a Bangladeshi identity expressed by British-born young women of Bangladeshi heritage in HE. I do not assume the ethnic category to have a given content, in terms for example of group members’ outlooks and values, and identification to mean therefore the same thing for different people. Rather, I intend to problematise the taken - for - grantedness of ethnic identities by paying particular attention to participants’ own understandings and construction of what it means to be Bangladeshi. In this sense, I am especially concerned with participants’ “self-identifications” intended “as processes developing from situated practices” (Colombo et al. 2009, p. 44). Analysis is aimed in particular at unravelling the inter - relations of these understandings and constructions with origins and trajectories of class, understood in a Bourdieusian sense as a complex amalgam of economic, social and cultural capital (Bourdieu 1986). The adoption of this analytical framework enables us to see how distinct though interrelated phenomena such as having a middle-class background and participating in HE can inform ethnic identification by affecting individuals’ access to differential configurations of material and symbolic capital.

In what follows, I critically review the major existing theorisations of the relation between socio-economic mobility and minority ethnic identification in light of recent research on experiences of middle-class and socially mobile individuals of minority ethnic origins. I also briefly consider how a Bourdieusian conceptual framework can contribute to the understanding of these processes. I then give an overview of the research context, design and methods before moving on to the empirical findings. Findings focus on different ways in which identification with ethnicity was presented by the young women who took part in this study and illustrate underlying dynamics. These constructions do not exhaust the range of positions expressed by respondents, which were varied and nuanced, but are especially illuminating of how ethnic identification can be shaped by socio-economic resources and trajectories. The subsequent discussion brings the main threads that emerge from these stories together and re - connects them with existing literature. Findings underscore the fluid, experientially - informed and relationally defined character of the meanings and value that are being attached to ethnic categories. They also point to the crucial role of economic, social and cultural capital in shaping these meanings. In this respect, it is suggested that upward social mobility can not only coexist with the assertion of a strong identification with one’s ethnicity, but also promote a re - evaluation and “re - claiming” of one’s ethnic (and religious) identity. Some reflections are made in the concluding paragraphs over implications for practice and further research.

Ethnic identification of minority ethnic middle-classes and socially mobile individuals

Two major theoretical frameworks have been developed to account for intergenerational processes of structural and cultural incorporation of immigrant groups in the country of settlement: classic, or “straight-line”, assimilation, and “segmented” assimilation (Thomson and Crul 2007). The first one, and the point of reference for others to follow, was initially advanced in relation to the experiences of European immigrants to the US (Warner and Srole 1945; Gordon 1964). Although with important amendments, this model’s central assumption has been more recently re-asserted with respect to newer waves of immigration from Asia, the Caribbean and Central America (Gans 1992; Alba and Nee 1997). That is, that following structural integration throughout generations we would observe a progressive decline in cultural, social and identity distinctions among ethnic groups, and as an end-product their complete dissolution. Yet, others have proposed a segmented assimilation model as better apt at capturing contemporary processes, especially as they are characterised by lower integration prospects for immigrants deriving from their non-white ethnic backgrounds and an increasingly polarised labour market (Portes and Zhou 1993; Zhou 1997). This framework sets out three possible trajectories for immigrants and their children to follow: cultural and socio-economic assimilation into the white middle-class; assimilation into a disadvantaged “underclass”; and upward economic mobility coupled with and aided by the preservation of ethnic bonds and cultural norms. In contrast to the straight-line model, it significantly points out that socio-economic integration is not necessarily preceded nor accompanied by cultural assimilation, and that a strong ethnic identification can in fact encourage occupational upward mobility and be retained in spite of it. Whilst this model acknowledges the resources that can be found within minority ethnic communities and the ways in which these can bolster “achievement” in education and employment (Shah *et al.* 2010), not much is being said about the influence of such an “achievement” on ethnic identities.

Studies looking more specifically at individuals’ ethnic identification and considering within-group differences have provided some support for the emergence of segmented assimilation patterns, where minority ethnic young people from middle-class families tended to identify in terms of parents’ nationality (Rumbaut 1994; Waters 1994). They have also revealed the occurrence of what has been described as “symbolic” ethnicity among the descendants of European immigrants in the US, marked by ethnic consumption patterns but devoid of ethnic group affiliations (Waters 1992), and of “reactive” ethnicity as strengthened ethnic identification in response to actual or perceived discrimination (Rumbaut 2008). This literature has importantly drawn attention to the diversity of content that ethnic identification can encompass and to the variation that exists within, as well as across, ethnic groups. Engaging critically with segmented assimilation theories, Neckerman *et al.* (1999) have called for better recognition of the distinctiveness of minority ethnic middle-class experiences and of their significance in shaping the cultural incorporation of immigrants and their descendants.

Research exploring the experiences of socially mobile individuals of minority ethnic origins has additionally shown how HE participation in can lead to the assertion of ethnic identities (Min and Kim 2000; Sloopman 2014, 2017). Looking at 1.5 and 2nd generation Asian-American professionals in the US, Min and Kim (2000) illustrate how most participants experienced psychological conflicts and resistance in relation to their ethnic identity during pre-college years. This was due to them being a minority ethnicity in school, experiencing discrimination from both white and black students, and wanting to “fit in”. Yet, this study also points to a newly found appreciation of one’s ethnic origins during college, with many of these young professionals developing a strong bi-cultural identity. The authors refer to the increased presence of other students of Asian-American background and availability of courses of study in subjects such as “Asian studies” as contributing to this re-evaluation and assertion. Sloopman (2014, 2017) reaches similar findings in relation to 2nd generation Dutch of Moroccan and

Turkish origins. Many of the socially mobile young adults she interviewed also displayed a rejection and subsequent assertion of their ethnic identities during their school and university years. For Sloodman's participants, it was especially the encounter with other highly educated, socially mobile Turkish and Moroccan Dutch which triggered a sense of identification and mutual understanding, and thus a re-evaluation of what it means to be Turkish or Moroccan. The analysis of the narratives of British-born young women of Bangladeshi origins presented here points to processes of "dis-identification" and "re-claiming" of ethnic identities which resonate with those highlighted by this research. As well as revealing additional factors which contribute to these dynamics, this paper further sheds light on these processes through the adoption of a Bourdieusian lens of analysis emphasising the importance of social structures and access to capital.

According to Bourdieu (1984; 1986), the class positionings and trajectories of individuals and groups produce dispositions (*habitus*) and give access to economic, social and cultural resources which are valued hierarchically. Classed dispositions and resources derive their specific value as forms of capital from the structure and logics of the social domains (*fields*), such as that of education, where agents engage. Agents' outlooks and practices are born out of the interplay among their dispositions, the capital they can access and the field's structure and logics (e.g. which resources are valued and what their "exchange rate" is). This conceptualization, I contend, can be fruitfully transposed to structures of power and inequality other than class such as ethnicity, race and gender. These can also be seen from such a perspective as being "relational ontological spaces" (Anthias 1998, p. 510), where individuals and group are hierarchically positioned with respect to one another according to the type and amount of resources they hold. Different ethnic groups are characterised in particular by power differentials among them in terms of access to material and symbolic resources, and of capacity to determine the value these resources hold in different contexts, i.e. to turn them into capital. Bourdieu's understanding of practice encourages us to consider which and whose resources and ways of being are accorded value, under what conditions they function as capital and to what effects. Central to this is his notion of symbolic violence. He writes in this respect that "individuals or groups are objectively defined not only by what they are but by what they are reputed to be", with this depending on both "material" and "symbolic properties" (Bourdieu 1990, p. 135). The symbolic value attributed to agents' properties, ranging from the body to ways of speaking, clothing and leisure activities, varies in relation to their position in social space, with properties associated to dominant groups being attributed more value (Bourdieu 1990, p.139). Symbolic violence is the process through which these arbitrary hierarchies of value are normalised and integrated in common, taken-for-granted beliefs, thereby contributing to legitimise the power of certain groups over others (Bourdieu 2002, p. 167).

Research context and methodology

UK residents of Bangladeshi origins represent, according to the latest Census, 0.8% of the overall population (ONS 2011f). Their very young age profile, with those born in Bangladesh accounting for less than half of the total (ONS 2011d, 2011g), attests to the increasing weight of younger, UK-born generations. 90% define themselves as Muslims (ONS 2011c). The vast majority either comes or has ancestors from the rural district of Sylhet and is of low socio-economic origins (DCLG 2009, ONS 2011a). As a whole, Bangladeshis represent one of the most disadvantaged ethnic groups in the UK on a number of levels. Unemployment and economic inactivity are especially high among both men and women, and those in employment are disproportionately concentrated in routine and semi-routine occupations, for example as kitchen labourers, sales assistants and cab drivers (Clark and Drinkwater 2007;

ONS 2012). For women, labour market participation is amongst the lowest of all major ethnic groups, with the latest Census data reporting only around 40% of those aged 25 to 49 as either working or looking for work (Nazroo and Kapadia 2013). Whilst this is to be attributed to a complexity of factors, among which structural inequalities figure prominently, common-sense discourses are still rife with culturalist explanations referring to patriarchal gender norms (Brah 2001; Women and Equalities Committee 2016). In the UK as in other European countries, women of South Asian Muslim background are often portrayed as being docile and submissive, deprived of agency and subdued to the will of their fathers or husbands (Ramji, 2003; Ahmad 2006). South Asians in general and Bangladeshis in particular are also frequently stereotyped as being backwards, uneducated and greedy, with young people deemed to be torn between two cultures (Alexander 2005; Sanchez 2012).

The relatively homogenous profile of this population is however becoming increasingly diversified in terms of both area of provenience and socio - economic distribution. Contributing to these changes are new waves of immigration, mainly formed by students and skilled migrants coming from non - Sylheti areas, and upward mobility among UK - born generations (DCLG 2009). Connected to this latter trend is that of growing participation and achievement in schooling and HE (Runnymede Trust 2012). Women of Bangladeshi background, in particular, have substantially increased their participation in HE over the last 20 years (Lymeropoulou and Parameshwaran 2015; Bagguley and Hussain 2016). While a break - down of data by gender is not available for the 1991 Census, statistics show that between 1991 and 2011 the proportion of Bangladeshis aged 16+ holding degree level qualifications has risen from 5% to 20%, with women accounting for around half of this latter percentage (ONS 2011b, 2011d; Lymeropoulou and Parameshwaran 2015).

This paper draws on the experiences of 21 British-born women of Bangladeshi heritage in their early 20s residing and attending university in London, where all of them but one were born and raised. London is home to around 58% of the Bangladeshi population residing in the UK, which is highly concentrated in specific areas (ONS 2011e). 19% of the total live in the Eastern borough of Tower Hamlets, where they account for 32% of residents. Tower Hamlets is one of the most deprived local authorities in England and a traditional area of settlement for Bangladeshi immigrants (DCLG 2009). Although unintentionally, this residential pattern was also manifested in my sample, where most of the young women interviewed originally came from this borough. At the time of the interviews, these young women were studying for a variety of undergraduate degrees at a range of differently ranked universities, spanning across the humanities, social sciences and “Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics” (STEM) subjects. Recruitment took place both by directly approaching potential participants at university entrances and public spaces and by establishing contacts through students’ Bangladeshi and Islamic societies. This latter approach might indeed have increased the likelihood of recruiting participants expressing a “strong” ethnic identification. This does not however undermine findings, as my intent is to examine and explain the reported identification processes rather than to argue for their prevalence.

Almost all these young women’s parents were born in Bangladesh and came to the UK at different points in their lives. Most fathers or stepfathers (15 out of 21) had jobs which can broadly be defined as working - class, for example as cooks, tailors, cab drivers and construction workers, four had what can be seen as middle - class jobs, either as business owners or as professionals, and one was unemployed. Most of the mothers (14) were housewives, apart from seven who worked at different levels in the social and education sectors. Except those participants whose parents had middle - class jobs, they were all of the first generation to go to university, although some had older siblings and family members who

went before them. While the class composition of my sample reflected the broader socio-economic profile of the student population of Bangladeshi background, involving more middle-class participants would have afforded the opportunity for a more detailed exploration of how “middle-classness” informed ethnic identification.

Data was gathered in two rounds of semi-structured interviews. It was then coded manually and with NVivo software, and underwent several stages of analysis in an iterative process where findings were fed back into theory and vice - versa. The first interview was exploratory and touched on several areas of interest including family background, schooling, friendships, future hopes and expectations, and relation with Bangladesh and Bangladeshi “culture” (e.g. music, movies and clothing). Emerging themes that appeared to warrant further delving into were investigated in more detail in a second interview. This covered social and academic experiences of HE, class identification, and reflections on ethnic, national and religious identity elicited through pictures chosen by participants to represent what it meant for them to be Bangladeshi, British and Muslim respectively. By asking participants to produce some pictures expressing the meanings they associated to being Bangladeshi, British and Muslim before we met for the second time, or to select them among those they already had, I hoped to encourage a deeper reflection than it would have been possible had I simply questioned them during the interview (Drew et al. 2010). These images provided a window on participants’ worlds, helped to stimulate the conversation and elicited the in-depth reflection I had hoped for, although in some cases more than others. Some participants noted they had found the task especially challenging as it required them to question usually taken for granted aspects of their identity. Giving them time to consider these elements outside of the interview situation afforded therefore the necessary space for related feelings to be brought into conscious perspective.

There is a risk, in framing the investigation of identities in terms of categories, that this might have encouraged participants to think about these aspects in an essentialising and exclusionary way. Yet, the responses that were given suggest that the open-ended nature of the questions offered in fact the possibility for exploring their mutual inter-relations. This supporting Croghan et al.’s (2008, p. 355) claim that “combining verbal and visual forms of self-presentation allows individuals more scope for presenting complex, ambiguous and contradictory versions of the self”. While recognizing that categories of identification are profoundly interlinked, with each of them shaping the meaning and content of the others, I have kept them distinct for analytical purposes to detangle the influence of each on the others. The findings reported in this article relate specifically to the interplay between class location and trajectory and the extent and meaning of ethnic identification. Religious faith was in fact indicated by all participants but the only non-Muslim as the most significant source of identity, and the meaning attributed to “being Muslim” appeared to be shaped like ethnic identification by experiences of university. In contrast to ethnic identification, however, the extent to which these young women identified as Muslim did not seem to change with class status and participation in HE. Religious identification and its interplay with other identity dimensions will be discussed in a separate article.

Empirical findings

1. How middle-class capital can help asserting ethnic identity

In her study of the experiences of young people of Afro-Caribbean origins, Reynolds (2006) draws attention to the significance of family practices in shaping ethnic self-identification. The findings I present in this section show how access to middle-class economic, social and cultural capital can inform these practices and be drawn on by middle-class parents

to encourage the development of a strong Bangladeshi identity. While not all middle-class parents engaged in this transmission, this is still worth noting as it contrasts with commonly held views and some academic literature that expect ethnic identification to be weaker in those who have established themselves as part of the middle-classes (Warner and Srole 1945; Gans 1992; Rumbaut 1994; Waters 1994; Thomson and Crul 2007; Slooman 2014, 2017).

Asked about “what made them Bangladeshi”, participants to this research largely referred to aspects of family life such as talking Bengali (or rather “Benglish”, a mix of Bengali and English) with parents and older relatives, the food they ate at home, the occasional wearing of traditional clothes and the customs maintained through family gatherings and social events. Differences existed in the extent to which these aspects were embedded in family practices and in the degree to which these young women “felt” the “Bangladeshi side” of their identity. Parents, who represented in this respect the primary source of socialisation, were more or less substantially involved in the maintenance and transmission of Bengali language, history and customs, depending on a number of factors. More recent experiences of migration and the presence of family members and/or economic interests in Bangladesh contributed to a stronger engagement, as did intensive relationships with the extended family and community. Also important were parental decisions regarding children’s education and the language spoken at home. Here, a focus on “integration” often meant that parents would give up on the transmission of Bengali language and history, as this tended to be considered irrelevant for formal educational and socio - economic advancement, and even “an extra burden” given the effort already involved in learning English.

How middle-class capital can be drawn on by parents in the transmission of a Bangladeshi identity is well illustrated by Flora’s example. Flora is from Leeds and came to London to study at a prestigious university. She expressed a high degree of identification with her Bangladeshi heritage and told me that “[she] was brought up very close to [her] roots”. Her parents, who both held degrees attained in Bangladesh as well as in the UK, were amongst the highest educated in my sample. Both were employed in solidly middle-class occupations in the medical and social sectors. Flora’s account reveals how they had always been very determined in fostering their daughter’s take-up of Bengali language and culture, and how they were aided in this endeavour by their socio - economic position. Financial availability meant for instance that the whole family could travel to Bangladesh relatively frequently (every one or two years), which gave her a better opportunity for “picking up the culture and understanding the culture”. Furthermore, parents’ connections with Bangladeshi cultural groups in Leeds contributed to Flora’s involvement in cultural functions, where she was encouraged to perform Bengali poetry, singing and dancing. These groups were largely composed by others of middle-class, Bangladeshi origins, thus providing access to middle-class cultural capital. Contrary to all young women of working-class background interviewed, moreover, her parents would actively promote her acquisition of Bengali language by not allowing any English to be spoken at home if not for homework. This emphasis on the take-up of Bengali can arguably be seen as being made possible by parents’ already acquired confidence in English and by the stronger sense of economic security that is generally associated with middle-class status, which made the transmission of the majority language less of a concern. In Flora’s case, therefore, economic, social and cultural resources enabled her parents to invest in the construction of her Bangladeshi identity, which she intended to pass on to her children.

2. Hierarchies of value and processes of “self-distancing”

In this section, I explore in more detail how the possibility for young people of minority ethnic heritage to hold positive feelings about their background is undermined by the combination of ethnicised and classed stereotypes and their consolidation as taken-for-granted beliefs.

One of the discursive strategies adopted by interviewees of middle-class background to allow for a positive sense of self as Bangladeshi was that of referring to the existence of “different types of Bangladeshis”, which typically involved a mix of ethnic and class attributes, and to associate themselves with a certain classed segment. Flora, for example, underscored the difference between Bangladeshis of Sylheti origins, who tend to experience considerable socio-economic deprivation and to have lower levels of education, and those from other regions of Bangladesh like her. While not linked to geographical provenance, this classed distinction was also evident in Shirina’s narrative. Similarly to Flora’s, Shirina’s parents both attended university in Bangladesh, but had to work their way up to establish themselves professionally in the UK after experiencing post - migration downward mobility. Her father had attained a UK degree and established himself in the legal profession, while her mother had progressed in her career to reach a managerial position. Like Flora, Shirina also felt close to the “Bangladeshi culture” and was strongly involved with the Bangladeshi society at her university. She was also student ambassador for a network of successful Bangladeshi professionals and helped other students to establish connections and gain work experience with these professionals. Yet, the excerpt below highlights how a positive self-identification as Bangladeshi is made possible for Shirina by stressing substantially classed distinctions within the ethnic group, whereby a contraposition is drawn between “hard - working families” and those “living on benefits”:

I felt really sad that so many [Bangladeshis] took advantage of the UK system, and they just sat there, their houses smell of curry, they don't dress well, and they can't speak English. And it just frustrated me that most of the UK was getting that impression of Bangladeshis. [...] But I always knew I was different from them, and my parents always taught me not to take advantage of what this country gives us, and they said no matter what, you need to struggle for what you want. Whereas a lot of people in Tower Hamlets don't do that, they sit at home, have 8 kids, get all the child benefits, sit at home with sky TV like satellites and enjoy their lives. Whereas with me my parents have always worked, like my dad was a student when he first came here, my mum worked to support my dad and then when he started working they both worked. (Shirina)

Throughout her account, Shirina weaves together common ethnic and classed stereotypes in the construction of “the typical Bangladeshi” from Tower Hamlets, whom she then presents herself and her family in contraposition to. In doing so, she contributes however to legitimise and perpetuate prevailing stereotypes of Bangladeshis as welfare scroungers and unwilling to integrate.

This strategy of distinction was not available to participants of working-class background. For some of these respondents, the lack of value and at times explicitly negative connotations that were attached to “being Bangladeshi / Asian” in the environment where they grew up had led them to distance themselves from their ethnic identity altogether. Here, I look at the experiences of two young women, Shay and Sultana, which illuminate this process of “self - distancing”.

While most participants in this study went to secondary schools and colleges with a high presence of pupils of Bangladeshi and more generally South Asian Muslim origins, Shay and Sultana were the only ones from working-class families who attended institutions where they were among the very few, and the only ones in their classes. Having moved from the inner city to the suburbs of London at around age 11, Shay went from being in a primary

school with an almost completely Bangladeshi, working-class student intake to a secondary school where pupils were largely white and middle-class. Likewise, Sultana found herself in a very different high school environment compared to her primary school years, as her mother had decided to place her in a Catholic institute with girls of mostly Black African and Afro - Caribbean backgrounds. In their accounts, they described the difficulties encountered in “fitting in” and how in order to do so they adapted their language, look, tastes, and generally their “way of being” to the new setting.

In this process of change and adaptation, both Sultana and Shay came to develop a negative conception of what they referred to as “the standard Bengali” / “the typical Asian”. This stereotypical depiction broadly considered Bangladeshis as “close minded”, “restrictive”, “nosy” and “gossipy”, and was mainly built on an elaboration of personal experiences abstracted from context and generalised. Structural factors contributing to certain behaviours and attitudes, such as residential segregation and discrimination, were easily overlooked, and these attitudes and behaviours were assumed to be characteristic of the “Bengali culture”. A further devaluation of their Bangladeshi and Asian identity also came from other people “making fun” and sometimes providing an explicitly negative image of associated cultural aspects. Sultana’s quote, reported below, testifies to the distress and internal struggle caused by the stereotypes imposed on her by her friends and schoolmates:

I used to not like being Bengali, because [...] I felt like I didn't fit in or whatever. [...] One of the other things I'm not really fond it's just because of all the negative stereotypes that are associated with Bengali people, and some of the stereotypes I guess are true in some cases. [...] Like Asian people smell of curry, they just eat rice and curry. Or like a lot of people used to get Asian people and Indian people mixed up, [...] they did use to say “oh, you bindi”, you this, you that, call me names. They use to say Bengali people are stingy with money. And it is like, even though I knew they were joking it kind of got to me for some reason. (Sultana)

As Shay and Sultana made these stereotypes their own, they constructed and presented their identity as being in contrast with the “way of being” they considered as “typical” of their ethnic group. They were keen to distance themselves, both figuratively and physically, from other Bangladeshis:

[If I'd stayed in Tower Hamlets] I'd have become just that person, just hang around with a group of Asians, not talking to anyone else, and it would have been horrible. Now I have barely any Bengali friends, barely any. Because I can't stand them to be honest, because they are so restrictive [...] Before I never used to hear anybody speaking in Bengali [where I live] but now there's more and more people. [...] I kind of like want to move again, I want to run away from them again. (Shay)

Like a typical Bengali teenager with the headscarf, she's expected to be kind of religious, very quiet, shy, she's kind of expected to hang around with other Asian girls. Whereas me, I don't have any Asian friends [...] and I'm not shy and I'm not quiet. [...] Personally I don't think I would find myself a Bengali or Asian person [...] I don't particularly see myself with Asian people. (Sultana)

In bringing to light the considerable impact that external perceptions of given ethnicities can have on those who belong to the ethnic group, these women’s stories contribute to expose the shifting, relational character of identification. They also make the ethnicised and classed hierarchies of value and status that enter into play in these processes manifest. Within the context of the secondary schools they attended, and I would suggest in reflection of the aforementioned widespread stereotypes, these women’s Bangladeshi and Asian identities did not provide a source of status, but rather the opposite (Warikoo 2011). For Shay in particular, whose school had a predominantly middle-class intake, the lack of value attributed by others and herself to “being Bangladeshi” was further linked to the ascription to such

an identity of working-class embodied expressions. For example in the case of her cockney (East London working-class) accent which she eventually dropped. The difficulties encountered in “fitting in” and the identity conflict that this generated finally led these women to adopt the cultural features of the groups that were dominant in their school setting and to distance themselves from their own ethnic group.

3. *Participation in higher education and the “re-claiming” of ethnic identities*

The above illustrated entrenchment of ethnicity and class in attributions of value is crucial in making sense of how upward mobility can facilitate the “re-claiming” of ethnic identities. Certain minority ethnicities are often associated in dominant imageries with working-class attributes, which contributes to their pathologisation (Wallace 2018). Normative middle - classness, on the other hand, is generally conflated with whiteness (Neckerman et al. 1999; Archer 2012). As more working-class minority ethnic students are entering HE, this provides them with increased opportunities to interact with like - minded peers of same ethnic origins but varied class backgrounds and trajectories. Similarly to what has been found by others (Min and Kim 2000; Slooman 2014, 2017), exposure to different and valued interpretive repertoires (i.e. understandings and constructions) of “what it means to be Bangladeshi” contributed for participants to this study to re-define their perception of their ethnic identity.

For these women, the intellectual and political engagement and social networks that came with university also prompted an increased awareness of and interest in issues of social justice and race relations. Growing knowledge of global structural inequalities and of the historical events that generated and sustained them represented an additional element contributing to the questioning of the status-quo and to the re - evaluation and “re - claiming” of one’s “roots”. Kanta, a young woman of working-class origins attending a top ranking university, told me for example:

I think now, when I get more involved in social activism and issues of social justice, I always remember the colonial parts of Bangladesh, and when I remember it I always feel like that’s something I can’t let go of and I have to keep hold of that part of my identity. (Kanta)

Although to varying degrees, this process of re - evaluation of one’s ethnic identity, aided by the accretion of social and cultural capital and increased reflexivity through HE, was common to many of the respondents. These dynamics are apparent in the extract below where Sadia, who also came from a working-class background and was attending another prestigious institution, discusses the picture she chose to represent what it meant for her to be Bangladeshi (Figure 1). Here, she talks in particular about proudly re - claiming her Bangladeshi heritage after a period of dismissal and detachment during secondary school:

[Figure 1 here]

When I was young I used to really like [henna] and I’d always want to wear it, then during my teenage years I was kind of embarrassed by it, and now again any opportunity I really like putting henna on and I think that also reflects my attitude towards the Bengali culture. [...] When I was in school I used to be picked to represent our school. So I was in an environment where, I think the teachers as well, it was like you would have to kind of transform yourself, be more essentially white or less Bengali and I think that’s where it stems from. [...] For me it’s even more important now, I really want to reclaim my culture. I think just learning about it in terms of society that we’re in. [...]. And you know, just reading, [...] you have all these people of colour just embracing their culture, and it’s actually more liberating when you own it. (Sadia)

In Sadia’s narration, multiple influences are evident which either favoured or deterred the formation of a positive sense of self as of Bangladeshi origins. Especially visible are the subtle

ways in which symbolic violence deprives this identity of value within mainstream institutional settings, and how critical racial awareness can have on the other hand a liberating potential.

Jamila is another working-class woman whose story is illustrative of this process. In the following quote, she reports how by learning more about Bangladesh and its history she developed a growing interest which led her to go to Bangladesh after 10 years. This increasing awareness eventually changed her perception of the country and its people, and made her more appreciative of her own ethnic background which had until then been “pushed down”. Her narrative exemplifies in this respect parents’ general lack of investment in the transmission of knowledge about Bengali language and history, and highlights the role that peer networks can have in promoting a re - evaluation of these aspects:

Only recently, in these past three years, I’ve started learning more about the Bangladeshi history, its culture, and sort of accepting that I’m Bangladeshi and being proud about it. [...] I went to Bangladesh during the summer after 10 years. [...] Because if you’re not growing up hearing about your culture and your history you’d never think to actually look into it. [...] I guess that’s because [our parents] think we’re not interested. [...] they don’t think to explain that kind of stuff and we have to push for it, and that’s something I want to do with the Bangladeshi Society as well, really push for the cultural and historical side. (Jamila)

The picture in Figure 2 was chosen by Jamila to represent what it meant for her to be Bangladeshi. As she explains in the description below, it symbolises the attachment she developed for the country and this part of her identity, and the beauty she now sees in it:

[Figure 2 here]

That picture for me represents sort of home in a sense and just not forgetting our ties with it because that’s what life is like for them. [...] You think of all the things you see on TV and all the poverty, the floods and the natural disasters and you don’t see it in that really beautiful light, and when I went to Bangladesh I saw it in a completely different light. (Jamila)

Importantly emerging from Jamila’s account is the role played by externally imposed images of Bangladesh (e.g. in the media) in shaping perceptions, and how negative representations can influence one’s understanding of their background.

Many other young women spoke of a newly discovered desire to “hold on to their roots” and transmit this sense of identity to their children. Even Sultana, who tended to dis-associate herself from her ethnicity, expressed a desire to get more in touch with this aspect of her identity and to enable this attachment for her future children. Once again, engagement with other Bangladeshis whom she valued positively appeared to facilitate this transition:

If I did have kids [...] I’d introduce them to, you know, this is your background, this is where you come from. Because even though I don’t particularly enjoy being Bengali but I still would like to embrace my background. [...] One of the student ambassadors, he’s Bengali and he started a Bengali Society. The same thing I’m telling you now I told him and he was like “oh, you shouldn’t be like that” [...] he was giving me this long talk and I kind of took it all in [...] so I ended up joining. (Sultana)

Involvement in HE and engagement with people from different backgrounds could also lead these women to adopt a more reflexive stance towards their Bangladeshi identity, where they expressed critique for certain aspects of culture while appreciating others. Many of them criticised for instance some of their parents’ views regarding requirements for the selection of potential husbands and excessive gossiping, while valuing other aspects of “Bengali culture” such as the high value attributed to family and the elders. This process of re - elaboration and

re - interpretation of one's "culture", where the content and meaning of practices is critically assessed and re - negotiated by those within the group boundaries, was also visible in relation to Islam. Here as well, HE represented an important arena of experiences and interactions that were key in shaping interviewees' constructions of what it meant for them to be Muslim. Attesting to the experientially - informed and dynamic character of ethnic and religious identities, and reflecting a common reasoning, Kanta noted how going to university had enabled her to reflect on her upbringing and on what she had learned "as both a Muslim and a Bengali", allowing her to "build upon it, understand it and value it".

Discussion and conclusions

This paper examined how middle-class status and participation in HE contribute to shape the ethnic identity construction and presentation of British-born young women of Bangladeshi heritage, and the meanings and value they attach to these identities. Empirical findings highlight three key points: how middle-class capital can be and was drawn on by participants and their parents in the construction of a "positive" ethnic identity; how intersecting ethnicised and classed hierarchies of value embedded in social and institutional settings can hamper the development of a positive conception of one's ethnicity; and how participation in HE can favour the re-evaluation and assertion of ethnic identities. I have shown that for some participants middle-class status enabled the affirmation of "confident" ethnic identities. Firstly, as access to economic, social and cultural capital facilitated parents' investment in the transmission of such an identity. Secondly, as it made it possible for these women to distance themselves from prevailing classed stereotypes of the ethnic group they belonged to and present to others a "positive" image of themselves as Bangladeshis. It has however been noted how, in this process, the adoption of discursive strategies that stress classed distinctions within a group can contribute to the legitimization of social inequalities. I have also argued that for some interviewees HE participation opened possibilities for the "re-claiming" of ethnic identities. One of the ways in which this happened was, similarly to what found by other studies (Min and Kim 2000; Slooman 2014, 2017), by promoting engagement with other "highly achieving", like-minded British-born young people of Bangladeshi background. Adding to this, intellectual and political involvement through courses of study and minority ethnic societies for example, increased for some of those who took part in this research the awareness of structural inequalities contributing to place their ethnicity in a subordinate material and symbolic position. The acquisition of social and cultural capital through participation in HE thus favoured the re-evaluation and assertion of ethnic identities by granting exposure to new and valued interpretive repertoires of "what it means to be Bangladeshi" and by making symbolic re-signification possible.

The findings presented here challenge straight - line theoretical approaches to the understanding of assimilation and certain public discourses insofar as they expect upward socio - economic mobility to be necessarily related with a waning ethnic identification (Warner and Srole 1945; Gans 1992; Rumbaut 1994; Waters 1994). On the contrary, the stories reported suggest that middle-class status and upward mobility can in fact coexist with the assertion and even support the "re - claiming" of ethnic identities, and provide some examples of underlying mechanisms. This (re)connection with one's ethnicity is not merely "symbolic" (Waters 1992), as it is associated with an interest in Bangladeshi language, history and traditions and with participation in co-ethnic networks, nor necessarily "reactive" (Rumbaut 2008). Analysis of these processes points instead to how access to economic, social and cultural capital can enable a more confident identification by affecting the content, meanings and value attached to ethnic categories that emerge as heterogeneous, fluid and relationally defined.

Ethnic identity has been deemed fundamental to the definition of one's self - concept and well - being (Phinney 1990; Yip 2016). For individuals of minority ethnic origins, it has been noted they often face tensions and dilemmas due to their group's "culture" and characteristics being essentialised and attributed low value within dominant constructions (Phinney 1990; Song 2001). The stories presented in this article further reveal how these stereotypes are substantially classed and how they can become internalised and shared by those within the group's boundaries with a considerable impact on self - understandings. The above considerations suggest the potential value, in countering negative representations, of initiatives directed on the one hand at exposing the structural factors underlying individuals' and groups' differential socio - economic positionings, and on the other at getting those within as well as outside the ethnic group to engage with varied interpretive repertoires of minority ethnicities. As highlighted by Jamila's and Sadia's experiences, activities taking place on campuses such as involvement in minority ethnic university societies and critical race education can promote a re-evaluation of one's ethnic identity and have an empowering potential. However, examples like those of Shay and Sultana also indicate that embedding these objectives in educational and recreational activities provided at a younger age and their extension to those who do not belong to the ethnic group could be more effective in tackling stereotypes.

This study has highlighted the importance of available interpretive repertoires of one's ethnicity for self-identification. It has further demonstrated how the interplay of dominant ethnicised and classed hierarchies of value can generate tensions and lead to "self-distancing", how middle-class capital can aid the assertion of a "confident" ethnic identity, and how the acquisition of social and cultural capital and increased reflexivity through participation in HE can enable the "re-claiming" of such an identity. New research could be usefully directed to better understanding the ways in which images of how certain minority ethnic groups "are" and of what they "do" are produced and circulated. Findings from this paper suggest that educational settings are critical in informing these perceptions. Further studies should thus be directed at interrogating, for instance, how related processes are differentially shaped by the socio-economic composition of the student body, curriculum, and teachers' expectations and practices. To more credibly put to the test the influence of middle-class capital and participation in HE on ethnic self-identification, the questions addressed by this paper should additionally be posed at a larger scale and involving generations beyond the second and third. The adoption of a mixed-methods approach and of a multi-dimensional concept of self-identification which allows to discern its various aspects (e.g. involvement in co-ethnic networks, use of language, attachment to traditions, and ethnic regard), would be in this sense especially desirable.

References

- Ahmad, F., 2006. The Scandal of "Arranged Marriages" and the Pathologisation of BrAsian Families. *Postcolonial People, South Asians in Britain, London: Hurst Publications.*
- Ahmad, F., 2007. Muslim women's experiences of higher education in Britain. *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, 24(3), 46.
- Ahmed, S., and Dale, A., 2008. Pakistani and Bangladeshi women's labour market participation. *Cathie March Centre for Census and Survey Research CCSR Working Paper.*
- Alba, R., and Nee, V., 1997. Rethinking assimilation theory for a new era of immigration. *International migration review*, 826-874.

- Alexander, C., 2006. Imagining the politics of BrAsian youth. *Ali, N., Kalra, VS, and Sayyid, S.*
- Anthias, F., 1998. Rethinking social divisions: some notes towards a theoretical framework. *The Sociological Review*, 46(3), 505-535.
- Archer, L., 2012. “Between authenticity and pretension”: parents', pupils' and young professionals' negotiations of minority ethnic middle - class identity. *The Sociological Review*, 60(1), 129 - 148.
- Bagguley, P., and Hussain, Y., 2016. Negotiating mobility: South Asian women and higher education. *Sociology*, 50(1), 43-59.
- Bourdieu, P., 1984. *Distinction: A social critique of taste. Cambridge: Harvard UP.*
- Bourdieu, P., 1986. “The forms of capital”. In: J. Richardson (ed.) *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*. New York: Greenwood, 241-258.
- Bourdieu, P., 1990. *The logic of practice*. Stanford: University Press.
- Bourdieu, P., 2002. *Language and symbolic power*. Harvard: University Press.
- Brah, A., 2001. “Race” and “culture” in the gendering of labour markets: South Asian young Muslim women and the labour market. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 19(3), 441-458.
- Cantle, T., 2001. *Community cohesion: A report of the independent review team.*
- Clark, K. and Drinkwater, S., 2007. *Ethnic minorities in the labour market. Dynamics and diversity*. Bristol: The Policy Press.
- Colombo, E., Leonini, L., and Rebughini, P., 2009. Different but not stranger: everyday collective identifications among adolescent children of immigrants in Italy. *Journal of ethnic and migration studies*, 35(1), 37-59.
- Croghan, R., Griffin, C., Hunter, J., & Phoenix, A. (2008). Young people's constructions of self: Notes on the use and analysis of the photo - elicitation methods. *International journal of social research methodology*, 11(4), 345-356.
- DCLG, 2009. *The Bangladeshi Muslim Community in England. Understanding Muslim Ethnic Communities*. London: Department for Communities and Local Government.
- Drew, S. E., Duncan, R. E., and Sawyer, S. M., 2010. Visual storytelling: A beneficial but challenging method for health research with young people. *Qualitative health research*, 20(12), pp. 1677-1688.
- Gans, H. J., 1992. Comment: Ethnic invention and acculturation, a bumpy - line approach. *Journal of American Ethnic History*, 42 - 52.
- Gordon, M. M., 1964. *Assimilation in American life: The role of race, religion, and national origins*. Oxford: University Press.
- Jivraj, S., 2012. How has ethnic diversity grown 1991 – 2001 – 2011? In: *The Dynamics of Diversity: evidence from the 2011 Census*. Manchester: Centre on Dynamics of Ethnicity.
- Kundnani, A., 2002. The death of multiculturalism. *Race & class*, 43(4), 67-72.
- Li, Y. and Heath, A., 2015. *CSI 10: Are we becoming more or less ethnically - divided?* Oxford: Nuffield College Centre for Social Investigation.

- Lymperopoulou, K. and Parameshwaran, M., 2015. "Is there an ethnic group educational gap?" In: S. Jivraj and L. Simpson (Eds.). *Ethnic identity and inequalities in Britain*. Bristol: Policy Press, 181-198.
- Min, P. G. and Kim, R., 2000. Formation of ethnic and racial identities: Narratives by young Asian-American professionals. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 23(4), 735-760.
- Nazroo, J. and Kapadia, D., 2013. Ethnic Inequalities in labour market participation? In: *The Dynamics of Diversity: evidence from the 2011 Census*. Manchester: Centre on Dynamics of Ethnicity.
- Neckerman, K. M., Carter, P., and Lee, J., 1999. Segmented assimilation and minority cultures of mobility. *Ethnic and racial studies*, 22(6), 945 - 965.
- ONS, 2011a. *2011 Census analysis: Ethnicity and the Labour Market, England and Wales*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011b. *2011 Census: CT0247 Ethnic groups by highest level of qualification by age by sex - National to local authority*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011c. *2011 Census: CT0575 2011 Census - Ethnic group (write-in response) by religion - England*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011d. *2011 Census: DC2101EW Ethnic group by sex by age*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011e. *2011 Census: KS201UK Ethnic group, local authorities in the United Kingdom*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011f. *Ethnic Group, 2011*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2011g. *Country of Birth (detailed) 2011*. Office for National Statistics.
- ONS, 2012. *Labour market status by ethnic group*. Office for National Statistics.
- Phinney, J. S., 1990. Ethnic identity in adolescents and adults: review of research. *Psychological bulletin*, 108(3), 499.
- Platt, L., 2005. *Migration and social mobility: the life chances of Britain's minority ethnic communities*. Policy Press.
- Portes, A., and Zhou, M., 1993. The new second generation: Segmented assimilation and its variants. *The annals of the American academy of political and social science*, 530(1), 74-96.
- Ramji, H., 2003. Engendering diasporic identities. *South Asian women in the diaspora*, 227-242.
- Reynolds, T., 2006. Caribbean families, social capital and young people's diasporic identities. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 29(6), 1087-1103.
- Rodríguez-García, D., 2010. Beyond assimilation and multiculturalism: A critical review of the debate on managing diversity. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 11(3), 251-271.
- Rumbaut, R. G., 1994. The crucible within: Ethnic identity, self - esteem, and segmented assimilation among children of immigrants. *International Migration Review*, 748 - 794.
- Runnymede Trust, 2012. *Briefing on Ethnicity and Educational Attainment, June 2012*. Runnymede.

- Sánchez, J. D., 2011. The South Asian Neighbour and Her/His Stereotype Goes Global. In *Pasado, presente y futuro de la cultura popular: espacios y contextos: Actas del IV Congreso de la SELICUP* (p. 17). Universitat de les Illes Balears.
- Shah, B., Dwyer, C., and Modood, T., 2010. Explaining educational achievement and career aspirations among young British Pakistanis: Mobilizing “ethnic capital”? *Sociology*, 44(6), 1109-1127.
- Slotman, M., 2014. Reinvention of ethnic identification among second generation Moroccan and Turkish Dutch social climbers. *New Diversities*, 16(1), 57 - 70.
- Slotman, M., 2017. Social mobility allowing for ethnic identification: reassertion of ethnicity among Moroccan and Turkish Dutch. *International Migration*.
- Song, M., 2001. Comparing Minorities' Ethnic Options Do Asian Americans Possess “More” Ethnic Options than African Americans? *Ethnicities*, 1(1), 57 - 82.
- Thomson, M., & Crul, M., 2007. The second generation in Europe and the United States: How is the transatlantic debate relevant for further research on the European second generation?. *Journal of ethnic and migration studies*, 33(7), 1025-1041.
- Wallace, D., 2018. Cultural capital as whiteness? Examining logics of ethno-racial representation and resistance. *British journal of sociology of education*, 39(4), 466-482.
- Warikoo, N. K., 2011. *Balancing acts. Youth culture in the global city*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Warner, W. L., and Srole, L., 1945. *The social systems of American ethnic groups* (Vol. 3). New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Waters, M. C., D' Innocenzo, M., and Sirefman, J., 1992. The construction of a symbolic ethnicity: Suburban white ethnics in the 1980s. *Immigration and Ethnicity: American Society—“Melting Pot” or “Salad Bowl”?*
- Waters, M. C., 1994. Ethnic and racial identities of second - generation Black immigrants in New York City. *International Migration Review*, 795 - 820.
- Women and Equalities Committee, 2016. *Employment Opportunities for Muslims in the UK*. London: House of Commons.
- Yip, T., 2016. *Benefits and challenges of racial / ethnic diversity: implication for adolescent identity and well - being*. Paper presented at: Harvard Graduate School of Education interdisciplinary colloquium, April 25th 2016.
- Zhou, M., 1997. Segmented assimilation: Issues, controversies, and recent research on the new second generation. *International migration review*, 975-1008.

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

